

Protection of stainless steel in 20% HCl by use of organic inhibitors

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Manuscript received 28 June 2005, revised 13 January 2006, accepted 16 October 2006

Abstract : The present work involve a study of corrosion rate, inhibition efficiency, surface coverage, heat of adsorption, heat of activation and other thermodynamic parameters are determined at different temperature with four organic compounds 2-mercaptobenzoxazol, 2-mercaptobenzimidazol, *N*-cetylpridiniumbromide and propargylbenzenesulphonate on the corrosion of stainless steel in 20% HCl. The compounds studied gave appreciable inhibition of stainless steel in 20% HCl. The effect of temperature on the inhibition efficiencies of these compounds show that it increased with temperature in all cases.

Keywords : Corrosion, corrosion protection, organic inhibitors, stainless steel.

A large variety of corrosive conditions are encountered in the different facets of industries from petroleum production through transportation to processing and storage of petroleum and petroleum products. Corrosion inhibitors are used to reduce corrosion damage in sub-surface equipments in both oil and gas wells. A majority of the corrosion inhibitors used in the petroleum industries are organic compounds¹. The composition and structure of the inhibitors change depending on the application which varies from purely aqueous to hydrocarbon systems. Although high temperature acid corrosion inhibitor used for oil well reservoir stimulation had been reported². The relevance of corrosion inhibitors in petroleum industry as a whole can be estimated from the available literature³. Nitrogen containing inhibitors have been reported to be effective in H₂S containing media. It is suggested that amine corrosion inhibitors interact with iron sulphide corrosion product layer to form surface complex⁴. It can be seen from the earlier work⁵ that amines and nitrogen containing heterocycle compounds had been studied extensively as inhibitors for corrosive media. An important criteria for the selection of inhibitors for hydrochloric acid corrosion is the synergism shown by some mixture compounds and such combinations are also used in commercial inhibitor formulations⁶. The role played by intensifier is to increase the secondary inhibition effect of the compounds used at high temperature.

Results and discussion

Effect of concentration : The effect of concentration of inhibition on the corrosion of stainless steel in 20%

hydrochloric acid with varying concentration of inhibitors, 2-mercaptobenzoxazol [IH(i)], 2-mercaptobenzimidazol [IH(ii)], *N*-cetylpyridiniumbromide [IH(iii)] and propargylbenzenesulphonate [IH(iv)] at 30 °C are presented (Table 1). IH(i), IH(ii) and IH(iii) are effective inhibitors, especially at concentration 5 mM and above. The highest inhibition efficiency of 87% was given by IH(i) at 10 mM concentration and IH(ii) gave 85% at the same concentration. In case of these two compounds there is sharp increase into inhibitors efficiencies on increasing the concentration from 1 mM to 10 mM. The plots of IE vs inhibitors concentration and log (θ/1 - θ) vs log C were found straight line with all the inhibitor tested.

Table 1. Inhibition of SS by different concentration inhibitors in 20% HCl at 30 °C

Inhibitors	C (mM)	K (mmpy)	log (θ/1 - θ)	IE (%)
IH(0)	0.0	0.088	0.0	0.0
IH(i)	1.0	0.028	0.25	68
	5.0	0.013	0.34	85
	10.0	0.011	0.43	87
	1.0	0.036	0.19	62
IH(ii)	5.0	0.016	0.28	81
	10.0	0.013	0.46	85
	1.0	0.032	0.11	63
IH(iii)	5.0	0.022	0.20	75
	10.0	0.020	0.30	77
	1.0	0.058	0.07	34
IH(iv)	5.0	0.047	0.12	46
	10.0	0.034	0.20	61

Effect of temperature : Table 2 gives the results of the immersion tests in the presence of 5 mM of different inhibitors at the five different temperatures 30–70 °C. Increase in temperature enhance the corrosion rate from 0.088 mmpy to 1.12 mmpy about 13 times. However in presence of inhibitors the trends seen to be different in many cases. The corrosion rate of stainless steel in the presence of 5 mM of 2-mercaptobenzoxazol initially increase 30 to 50 °C then decrease to 0.018 mmpy at 70 °C. The inhibition efficiency of the compound increases from 85 to 98% on going from 30 to 70 °C, 2-mercaptobenzimidazol also show a similar trend but to a lower extent with inhibition efficiencies increasing from 82 to 96%. The inhibition efficiency of *N*-cetylpyridiniumbromide decreased from 76 to 70% on going from 30 to 40 °C and then increased to 95% at 70 °C. In the case of propargylbenzenesulphonate the trend is not very regular and the inhibition efficiencies varied from 65 to 83%.

Many of the compounds studied such as propargylbenzenesulphonate and 2-mercaptobenzimidazol are compounds with multiple points of attachment of metal surface and many of them are capable of forming complexes with metal ions. These metal inhibition complexes formed on the surface further protect the metal from attack. In some cases this complex formation may also be facilitated by the higher temperature.

Thermodynamic parameters are given in Table 3. obtained from plot of $\log K$ vs $1/T$. Activation energy for the corrosion reaction of stainless steel in hydrochloric acid increases in the presence of inhibitors. The activation energy without inhibitors is found to be 10.45 kJ/mol. In the presence of inhibitors it increases as shown in the Table 3. However in the case of 2-mercaptobenzimidazol the heat of activation is found to be much less than 2-mercaptobenzoxazol and it does not give any indication of its very good inhibition efficiency. On the other hand, propargylbenzenesulphonate, 2-mercaptobenzoxazol and *N*-cetylpyridiniumbromide had increased the activation energy of almost the some extent and propargylbenzenesulphonate increased it most. The order of activation energies in case of these inhibitions is $IH(iv) > IH(i) > IH(ii) > IH(iii)$ and in all cases it can not be correlated to their efficiencies.

The heat of adsorption of inhibitors was calculated from the plots of $\log (\theta/1 - \theta)$ vs $1/T$. From the slopes of the lines the heats of adsorption were calculated (Table 3). Obviously a higher value of heat of adsorption show a stronger adsorption and hence a better inhibition. This is observed in the case propargylbenzenesulphonate, 2-mercaptobenzoxazol and *N*-cetylpyridiniumbromide. The value of heat of adsorption for these compounds range from 34.45 kJ mol⁻¹ to about 45.93 kJ mol⁻¹ of which propargylbenzenesulphonate show the maximum heat of adsorption.

Table 2. Inhibition of SS by 5 mM of different inhibitors in 20% HCl at different temperature

Inhibitors	Temp.	30 °C	40 °C	50 °C	60 °C	70 °C
IH(i)	K_o	0.086	0.186	0.207	0.925	1.120
	K	0.013	0.020	0.026	0.019	0.018
	IE (%)	85	89	87	96	98
	θ	0.85	0.89	0.87	0.96	0.98
IH(ii)	K_o	0.088	0.186	0.207	0.925	1.120
	K	0.016	0.031	0.027	0.026	0.025
	IE (%)	82	81	86	97	96
	θ	0.82	0.81	0.86	0.97	0.96
IH(iii)	K_o	0.088	0.186	0.207	0.925	1.120
	K	0.022	0.050	0.041	0.045	0.510
	IE (%)	76	70	77	94	95
	θ	0.76	0.70	0.77	0.94	0.95
IH(iv)	K_o	0.088	0.186	0.207	0.925	1.120
	K	0.030	0.042	0.068	0.159	0.185
	IE (%)	65	77	70	82	83
	θ	0.65	0.77	0.70	0.82	0.83

Table 3. Thermodynamical parameters of different inhibitors for SS in 20% HCl

Inhibitors	Q (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔE (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	ΔG (kJ mol ⁻¹)
IH(0)	-22.50	10.98	-20.29	-97.29	-21.87
IH(i)	-45.93	30.62	-31.45	-98.97	-41.43
IH(ii)	-38.28	11.48	-12.31	-99.97	-22.30
IH(iii)	-34.45	24.88	-25.71	-235.08	-49.21
IH(iv)	-49.76	38.28	-39.11	-399.91	-70.10

Plots of $\log K$ vs $1/T$ are linear for all system. The values of enthalpy, entropy and free energy are given in Table 3. The data shows that the complex formation reactions in solution are exothermic ($-\Delta H$) and spontaneous ($-\Delta G$) in all cases. Further the negative values of the entropy changes indicate that the reactions suffer a loss of some degree of freedom during complex processes. It is also evident that the values of G , H and S are higher for IH(i), IH(ii) and IH(iv), so it form strong complex with metal⁷. The order of values for G , H and S is IH(iv) > IH(i) > IH(ii) > IH(iii).

Potentiostatic polarization : The cathodic and anodic total slopes for the potentiostatic polarisation curves have increased on the addition of inhibitors (Table 4, Fig. 1). The corrosion rates obtained from this study is comparable with that of immersion test under the same conditions. It is observed that all four inhibitors have produced parallel displacement of both cathodic and anodic Tafel lines to more negative or positive values relative to the ones produced in absence of inhibitor. This indicates that these inhibitors behave as mixed type inhibitors and that inhibition takes place by adsorption on metal surface. The values of corrosion current density and corrosion rates decrease with addition of inhibitor. The increase of inhibition efficiency with increase in inhibitor concentration supports the adsorption mechanism for inhibition⁷. The value of inhibition efficiency shows that IH(i) has the lowest inhibitive effect followed by IH(ii), IH(iii) and IH(iv) has the highest inhibitive effect.

Mechanism of inhibition : It is reported that the π -electron density in the hetero atoms in both nonprotonated and protonated 2-mercaptobenzimidazol is higher at the sulphur atom than the nitrogen atom⁸. In the strongly acidic 20% HCl medium, the compound get protonated and this reduces the π -electron densities at both sulphur and nitrogen atoms. It is likely that a metal inhibitor bond formed both on account of the sulphur and nitrogen atoms as well as the π -electron of the benzene ring. In strongly acidic solution the compound can inhibit the anodic process by the adsorption on the metal surface

Table 4. Potentiostatic polarization of different inhibitors for SS in 20% HCl at 5 mM inhibitor concentration

Inhibitors	β_c (mV)	β_a (mV)	I_{cr} (μA)	IH (%)
IH(0)	0.50	0.48	10.0	0.0
IH(i)	0.55	0.49	8.0	25
IH(ii)	0.52	0.53	8.5	17
IH(iii)	0.57	0.56	7.0	42
IH(iv)	0.61	0.58	7.5	33

and cathodic process by the reduction of the protonated form to non-protonated form.

The inhibition effect of 2-mercaptobenzimidazol is basically through the chemisorptions of the compound on the metal surface through the many reaction centres such as the sulphur atom, two nitrogen atoms and the π -electron of the benzene ring.

The positive inhibitor cation on adsorption on the metal surface create a positive potential barrier which mainly inhibits the cathodic reaction. The anodic reactions are inhibited only at higher concentration.

In the present work we have studied propargyl-benzenesulphonate to understand the effect of the acetylenic functional group on the inhibition of steel corrosion. This compound also has a sulphonate ester functional group that has high chelating tendency and form strong complex with metal. The thermodynamic parameters also indicate stronger interaction between the metal and inhibitor.

Experimental

The experiments were performed to study the inhibition effect of some organic compounds containing hetero atoms such as nitrogen sulphur and acetylenic groups on stainless steel in 20% HCl. The corrosion rate is determined by gravimetric method and potentiostatic polarization.

Stainless steel coupons were ruffed with emery paper of increasing fineness and then washed with double distilled water and finally degreased with acetone and dry with air dryer. The test solution was prepared by adding

Fig. 1. Polarization curves for stainless steel in 20% HCl in the presence of various inhibitors at 5 mM concentration.

required amount of A.R. grade hydrochloric acid to double distilled water for each test 400 ml solution were taken in 500 ml beakers. The requisite amounts of inhibitors were added to this solution before the tests. Stainless steel type 316 was used for the test.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Department of Chemistry, Patna University and Indian School of Mines, Dhanbad for providing laboratory facilities.

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